

Nanoparticles Imaging Technology for Scientists

CD BioSciences, a US-based biotechnology company focusing on the development of imaging technology, has recently announced the launch of [Nanoparticles Imaging Technology](#) to help researchers visualize cell functions and biological processes of living bodies in a non-invasive manner for accurate early diagnosis of diseases.

Nanoparticles are becoming a versatile tool in biomedical applications, especially in the field of biomedical imaging. Nanoparticles can be utilized for diagnosis, monitoring of physical and pathological processes, therapy and control of biological systems. They are typically smaller than 100 nm in size and can be made of materials with different chemical properties, most commonly metals, metal oxides, silicates, polymers, carbon, lipids and biomolecules. In addition, nanomaterials have diverse surface chemical properties, unique magnetic properties, and tunable absorption and emission properties, and can therefore be designed with different sizes, shapes, chemical surface properties, and hollow, porous, or solid structures.

Nanomaterials have become one of the most powerful imaging tools in molecular imaging due to their diversity and uniqueness. CD Biosciences can synthesize different types of nanoparticles and apply nanotechnology to molecular imaging, allowing researchers to observe cellular functions and biological processes in living organisms in a non-invasive manner for accurate early diagnosis of diseases.

Applications

In vivo imaging of targeted drug delivery

Tissue imaging and analysis, and cell imaging analysis

Digital pathology & imaging analysis

Detect early-stage diseases, e.g., cancer, cardiac diseases, inflammation, and stroke.

CD BioSciences possesses a professional team with extensive work experience in the imaging field. The team is able to provide clients with personalized imaging services to meet their research needs in the fields of biology, microbiology, medicine and food.

For customers interested in learning more about Nanoparticles Imaging Technology, please visit CD BioSciences at <https://www.bioimagingtech.com/>.

About CD BioSciences

CD BioSciences is a biotechnology company committed to the development of imaging technology for many years. Its scientists can utilize high-content imaging, nanoparticle imaging, imaging flow cytometry, time-lapse imaging, and other techniques to image cell structure, cell migration, cell proliferation, pathogen

infection mechanisms, and interactions between protein molecules. In addition, the team is capable of applying powerful analytical software to capture images of cellular structure, subcellular, or tissues to obtain useful information.